

TRAIN4EU

Workpackage 5 – Mainstreaming Open Science

Task 5.3 University Centres of Support for Open Science

TOOLKIT FOR OPEN SCIENCE ADVOCACY

How to use this Toolkit?

This Toolkit's structure is designed as simple and linear, avoiding interactive elements.

You can download and use each part of this Toolkit separately.

Go to

Toolkit 1

Part 1

Download

Go to

Toolkit 1

Part 2

Download

Go to

Toolkit 2

Download

Go to

Toolkit 3

Download

EUROPEAN
UNIVERSITY
ALLIANCE

TRAIN4EU project structure

Work Package 5

Mainstreaming Open Science

Task 5.1

Protocol for Base-Lining and Best-Practice Assessment of Mainstreaming Open Science

Task 5.2

Identifying Best Practices Concerning Open Science Publication and Open Research Data

Task 5.3

University Centres of Support for Open Science

Work Package 5

Mainstreaming Open Science

Task 5.3 University Centres of Support for Open Science

The main objective of Task 5.3 was to explore and understand the involvement of university libraries in supporting Open Science (OS) and assisting researchers.

We identified and collected best practices from the 4 EU+ Alliance universities, seeking inspiration from proven ideas and strategies for effectively meeting the needs of scientists in the context of Open Science.

As part of our project, we developed a toolkit for Open Science advocacy. This toolkit could serve as a resource for promoting and facilitating Open Science practices and initiatives.

Task 5.3

University Centres of Support for Open Science

Case 1

**Research Data
Management
and FAIR Data**

Case 2

**Responsible
Publishing**

Case 3

**Citizen
Science**

Case 1: Research Data Management and FAIR Data

Part 1

Toolkit 1, part 1 – Description of job profiles for the new data roles at universities – is based on Case #1 Research Data Management (RDM) and FAIR Data.

It defines of the required skills and competencies for seven research data management (RDM) professionals.

Job profiles for the new data roles

1

Data Protection Officer (DPO)

2

Research Administration Officer

3

Tech Transfer Officer

4

IT Officer

5

Data Scientist / Data Engineer

6

Data Steward / Data Librarian

7

Ethics Committee Administrator

Data Protection Officer (DPO)

In compliance with the regulations, Data Protection Officer ensures securing personal data by identifying risks and implementing procedures during operations and processing. They also organize consulting sessions to raise awareness on these data protection issues.

Hard skills

Soft skills

- Communication skills
- Leadership skills
- Project management
- Didactic skills
- User and domain analysis
- Liaison skills

Project management

- Legal, audit and risk management

Project monitoring

- Monitoring and reviewing personal data handling

Policy awareness

- EU and global privacy laws, legislation and policies
- Technology provisions
- Outsourcing agreements

Data security expertise

- Legal constraints related to data storage
- IT and computer security

Legal expertise

- Legal aspects of open data
- Having knowledge of data sharing agreements, privacy, consent and data management
- Interpretation of license agreements
- Using third-party data regarding data management
- Personal and sensitive data protection and their processing
- Monitoring compliance with data protection standards
- Personal & sensitive data sharing
- EU and global privacy laws, legislation
- Having deep knowledge about GDPR

Research Administration Officer

The Research Administration Officer ensures compliance with regulations relating to external funding and support research project management. They coordinate proposal activities according to institutional, (inter)national and agency requirements and monitor contracts and grant administrations.

Hard skills

Soft skills

- Communication skills
- Leadership
- Raising awareness
- Liaison skills
- Problem solving skills and applied reasoning
- Didactic Skills

Data Management Plan (DMP)

- Knowledge on DMP writing in funding proposal

Policy awareness

- Assure the proper application of policies and regulations
- Interpret and communicate applicable policies, procedures, and guidelines to project leaders

Project management

- Funding requirements
- Manage multiple projects under tight deadlines
- Risk assessment

Project planning

- Preparation of grant applications
- Knowledge and application of standard budgeting procedures
- Knowledge of the electronic grants process
- Check and verify budget calculations
- Analyze the eligibility of matching fund contributions

Tech Transfer Officer

Technology Transfer Officer is in charge of commercialization and transferring research results and findings to industry. In order to merge research impact and financial benefit, they carry out various commercial activities to introduce research developments to industry, often serving as a connection between university and enterprise.

Hard skills

Soft skills

- Communication skills
- Leadership
- Raising awareness
- Liaison skills
- Project management
- Project planning
- Project monitoring
- Entrepreneurial mindset
- Analytical skills

Project planning

- Planning and coordination for strategic project collaborations and commercialization opportunities

Project commercialization

- Having experience working in both sectors (university and industry) to establish industry-academia partnerships
- Commercialization of research data

Project valorization

- Communication of project through activities
- Reviewing patent application
- Expressing opinion on patents and industrial clauses

Legal knowledge

- General legal aspects of open data
- Research data patenting
- PI, copyrights and licenses
- Inventions
- Contract negotiations with companies relating to stakeholders, technology transfer agreements and licenses, monitor
- Monitoring of emerging trends, sector analysis and industrial organization
- Provide market research and analysis on technology commercialization
- Marketing of project through activities
- Manage information systems to ensure underlying support for commercial opportunity disclosures, patent and contract administration processes
- Commercialization of IP through licensing
- Creation of spin-off companies

IT Officer coordinates the administration of information technology (IT) services of the university by providing technical services on issues related to infrastructure, software and applications.

Hard skills

Soft skills

- Communication skills
- User and domain analysis
- Didactic and pedagogical skills
- Analytical and problem solving skills
- Liaison skills
- Leadership skills
- Project management

Project management

- Technical assistance and maintenance on projects

Technical equipment expertise

- Having knowledge about HPC, supercomputers, mass spectrometry
- Installing, maintaining and upgrading servers
- Troubleshoot existing systems (hardware, network, software)
- Assists with the installation, configuration and maintenance of computers, workstations and/or other related equipment and devices
- Recommendation of solutions relating to hardware and software acquisitions and/or network updates
- Perform routine preventive maintenance on systems software, applications, hardware, networking, and communications

Software & application expertise

- Software & application installation, configuration and management
- Customized research application
- Troubleshoot system and network problems, diagnosing and solving hardware or software faults

Data storage expertise

- Having experience on data storage management
- Having knowledge about data storage options (cloud based, servers, storage facilities)

Policy awareness

- Implementation of policies and standard
- Review of vendor contracts and coordinates IT purchases
- Assuring the implementation of university IT operations, projects, and programs

Data Scientist / Data Engineer

Data Scientist or Data Engineer is an expert in data processing, able to evaluate data quality, extract relevant knowledge, and represent such knowledge, encompassing researchers and PhD students. Data engineers are more involved in migrating data, handling format-related issues, and managing provenance information.

Hard skills

Soft skills

- Communication skills
- User and domain analysis
- Analytical and problem solving skills
- Liaison skills
- Leadership skills
- Project management

Software & application expertise

- Software & application installation, configuration and management
- Customized research application
- Troubleshoot system and network problems, diagnosing and solving hardware or software faults

Technical equipment expertise

- Having knowledge about HPC, supercomputers, mass spectrometry
- Installing, maintaining and upgrading servers
- Troubleshoot existing systems (hardware, network, software)
- Assists with the installation, configuration and maintenance of computers, workstations and/or other related equipment and devices
- Recommendation of solutions relating to hardware and software acquisitions and/or network updates
- Perform routine preventive maintenance on systems software, applications, hardware, networking, and communications

Data analysis expertise

- Data collection methods and technologies
- Data preparation, cleaning techniques
- Machine learning methods
- Programming languages
- Data collection methods and technologies
- Data mining and harvesting (API, scripts, etc.)
- Data visualization and graph databases

Data engineering expertise

- Developing tools and applications to cover data lifecycle
- Designing cloud computing services
- Big data techniques for large data processing and data integration
- Data modelling of complex systems
- Implementing systems for data access and data security
- Databases and data warehouses expertise (develop, build, operate)

Data Steward / Data Librarian

Data librarians, professional library staff specializing in Research Data Management (RDM), serve as metadata specialists, handle data transfer, assure long-term storage, and may also function as administrators of digital libraries by organizing catalogues.

Hard skills

Soft skills

- Communication skills
- Didactic and pedagogical skills
- Leadership
- Raising awareness
- Liaison skills
- Project management
- Project planning
- Project monitoring
- Analytical and problem-solving skills

DMP

- Providing recommendation of tools & best practices
- Familiarization data life cycle within a field of practice
- Expertise on DMP drafting and its reviewing

FAIR data

- FAIR (meta)data management and governance
- Having knowledge about FAIR tools and services

Ethical knowledge

- Research ethics related to a scientific domain
- Ethical and responsible data use and share

Legal knowledge

- Legal aspects of open data, data access, reuse and share

Data organization and curation

- Expertise on (meta)data standards, schemas, vocabularies and ontologies
- Data documentation
- Metadata conversion
- Improving quality of shared (meta)data

Data archiving and preservation

- Long-term preservation solutions (arrangement, sorting rules, conservation time, required metadata)
- Authorization management to access archived data

Data share

- Expertise on repositories & data catalogues
- Making research data available

Policy awareness

Technical and computational skills

- Programming languages (use of Python/R)
- Data extraction methods (e.g. via APIs, web scraping)
- Data cleaning, analysis
- Topic modelling and ontologies
- Social network analysis
- Data visualization

Ethics Committee Administrator

Ethics Committee Administrator evaluates the ethical issues of the research protocol regarding the protection of research participants and data. They review and give ethical opinions on these protocols to ensure compliance with laws and recommendations.

Hard skills

Soft skills

- Communication skills
- User and domain analysis
- Liaison skills
- Organization and time management skills
- Maintain high standards of confidentiality
- Project management

Ethical expertise

- Research ethics related to a scientific domain
- Appreciation of ethical issues in relation to research and the requirements of a process to review these issues
- Knowledge about ethical issues about data sharing
- Having experience of handling sensitive personal data, and the associated audit processes

Project management

- Risk assessment
- Compliance assurance

Project monitoring

- Having experience of acting as a source of expert advice
- Communicating complex or specialized information
- Operating ethical review process

Policy awareness

- Familiarity with current legislation, standards and codes of practice relating to human research ethics
- Capacity to develop familiarity with current legislation, standards and codes of practice (ex. relating to animal welfare and biosafety), including their implications for the conduct of research in a university environment

Case 1: Research Data Management and FAIR Data

Part 2

Toolkit 1, part 2 – Training in open data support (topics set) – is based on Case #1 Research Data Management (RDM) and FAIR Data.

It includes suggested topics to be used in four training sessions.

Training in open data support – topics set

1

Legal issues: intellectual property

2

Personal data, GDPR and anonymization

3

Introduction to data security

4

The basics of ethics in research

Training in open data support

Legal issues: intellectual property

Training audience

- PhD students
- Researchers
- Staff

Previous knowledge

None required

Aims of the training

- Understand the legal framework of intellectual property
- Understand the rights that apply to research data:
 - Open data: public sector data, geographical data, environmental data
 - Protected data: database rights, patents, health data, privacy, trade secrets, state secrets, etc.
- Distinguish reusable data from protected data
- Know the different types of open/free licenses: public domain licenses, permissive licenses, copyleft
- Know the different types of content to which these licenses apply: research data, databases, open-source software, etc.

Training in open data support

Legal issues: intellectual property

Intellectual
property
rights

Copyright

- artistic, ▪ musical
- dramatic ▪ for texts, images, videos, music

Industrial property

- trademark ▪ patent
- design ▪ database
- trade secret

Reusable
or
protected
data?

Identify the legal notices and terms of use on the datasets

Open/free
licenses

Public domain licenses ▪ Creative Commons: CCo ▪ Public Domain Dedication and License
Permissive licenses ▪ Apache License ▪ BSD License ▪ MIT License ▪ Creative Commons Attribution: CC:BY
Copyleft ▪ GNU General Public License ▪ Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike: CC:BY-SA

Open
or
protected
data

Open data ▪ Public sector data: PSI Directive ▪ Geographical data: INSPIRE Directive (INfrastructure for SPatial InfoRmation in the European community) ▪ Environmental data: Aarhus Convention (Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters)

Protected data, use cases ▪ database rights ▪ patents: use case on a research project with a company that wants to file a patent ▪ health data: use case on a research project with a clinical trial ▪ privacy: sociological research project with a survey ▪ trade secrets: example of a grant agreement with a confidentiality clause between the research team and the partner company ▪ state secrets: dual use technologies

1

Plan and activities

Training in open data support

Legal issues: intellectual property

Examples according to the type of content

Research data ▪ Creative Commons
Databases ▪ PDDL, ▪ ODC By ▪ ODC ODbL
Open-source software ▪ GNU Licenses

References

Engelhardt, Claudia, et al. (2022). D7.4 How to Be FAIR with Your Data. A Teaching and Training Handbook for Higher Education Institutions.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5837500>

Excercise

Find your open license <https://ufal.github.io/public-license-selector/>

Training in open data support

Personal data, GDPR and anonymization

Training audience

- PhD students
- Researchers
- Staff

Previous knowledge

None required

Aims of the training

- Know legal framework for personal data: GDPR
- Know what is personal data
- Differentiate between personal and sensitive data
- Understand the data protection principles of GDPR
- Understand legal bases for processing personal data
- Know your obligations for a research project
- Discover anonymization tools

2

Plan and activities

Training in open data support Personal data, GDPR and anonymization

GDPR

- What is it, who is affected?
- Obligations of a research project

Discussion: Do you collect personal data? Do you think you are you in compliance with GDPR?

Personal data

Any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ▪ an identifiable person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly ▪ examples: name, identification number, location data, online identifier (for ex.: personal data collected for this training)

Discussion: Can your date of birth and your personal contact details be collected for this training?

Sensitive data

- Personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs
- Trade-union membership
- Genetic data, biometric data processed solely to identify a human being
- Health-related data
- Data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation

2

Plan and activities

Training in open data support Personal data, GDPR and anonymization

Data protection principles of GDPR

- Lawfulness, fairness and transparency
- Purpose limitation
- Data minimization
- Accuracy
- Storage limitation
- Integrity and confidentiality
- Accountability

GDPR and your research project

Before the project ▪ contact your Data Protection Officer (DPO) ▪ write information for the records of processing activities ▪ write information for the records of processing activities ▪ write information sheets about the project for people to be interviewed and prepare consent forms
During the project ▪ regularly check access to the database or files containing personal data, and delete access for people who have left the project
After the project ▪ verify the retention period of personal data ▪ delete data after the specified retention period

Legal bases for processing personal data

- Consent
- Contract
- Legal obligation
- Vital interests of the data subject
- Public interest
- Legitimate interests

Anonymization tools

- Amnesia (OpenAire)
- K-anonymity principles

Exercise: Test the online version of Amnesia [Materials to be provided to participants: personal data sheets with false information about imaginary people]

2

Plan and activities

Training in open data support

Personal data, GDPR and anonymization

Engelhardt, Claudia, et al. (2022). D7.4 How to Be FAIR with Your Data. A Teaching and Training Handbook for Higher Education Institutions. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5837500>

European Commission. What personal data is considered sensitive?
https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/rules-business-and-organisations/legal-grounds-processing-data/sensitive-data/what-personal-data-considered-sensitive_en

GDPR.eu. Complete guide to GDPR compliance. <https://gdpr.eu/>

OpenAIRE. A complete k-anonymity scenario.
<https://amnesia.openaire.eu/Scenarios/AmnesiaTutorialKANon.pdf>

OpenAIRE. Amnesia. <https://amnesia.openaire.eu/>

References

Training in open data support

Introduction to data security

Training audience

- PhD students

Previous knowledge

None required

Aims of the training

- Understand the different levels of data security
- Be aware of the risks associated with research data
 - understand the causes of data loss
- Discover methods for protecting research data
 - know methods for protecting data on a computer or hard drive
 - know methods to protect data during transmission or sharing
- Discover methods for backing up data

Training in open data support

Introduction to data security

Information
classification
types
example

- Open access:
 - no particular risk in case of data loss
 - e.g., course notes, downloading a completely open dataset
- Restricted access:
 - data that require special monitoring
 - who can access it, for how long?
 - should they be subject to special security measures (encryption, offline storage)
- Embargo:
 - data that can be opened at the end of a period to be defined
 - for example, at the end of a project, after the publication of an article
- Closed access:
 - sensitive data which consultation and analysis is strictly controlled
 - access is verified and login information is kept
 - these data cannot be downloaded or transmitted under any circumstances

Risks

- Data loss
 - save your thesis drafts and manuscripts!
 - avoid USB keys for essential data
- Data theft
 - difficult to predict
 - solution: back up your data!
- Security breach (intrusion)
 - complicated to detect
 - check with your IT department
- **Discussion:** have you ever had any of these problems? Were you able to identify the causes?

Causes

- Lack of maintenance of the computer or the USB key
 - importance of updates
 - regular scanning with antivirus software
- Lack of data security during transmission
 - transfer by email
 - transfer via a private cloud that does not comply with the GDPR

3

Plan and activities

Training in open data support

Introduction to data security

Data protection methods

- On a computer or hard drive
 - create strong passwords to access the computer
 - check the access rights of each user if the computer is shared between several people
 - protect sensitive data in specific folders, with controlled access and, if necessary, encryption
 - reserve USB storage for temporary data, back it up as soon as possible
- During transmission
 - recommendation: do not send sensitive data by email
 - use your university's secure clouds (explain the risks of clouds like Dropbox or Google Drive)

Back up methods

- 3-2-1 rule
 - there should be 3 copies of data
 - stored on 2 different devices
 - with 1 copy being off-site

Discussion: How do you back up your data? Did you know 3-2-1 rule?
- If backups are automated, check the data retention period to make sure you can recover it in case of an incident

References

Montclair State University. Data Security in Research. <https://www.montclair.edu/institutional-review-board/data-security-in-research/>

Training in open data support

The basics of ethics in research

Training audience

- PhD students
- Staff

Previous knowledge

None required

Aims of the training

- Be aware of the ethics principles
- Know the European framework for research involving the human subjects
- See an example of the Horizon Europe self-assessment form
- Know the ethics committees and the institutional review boards

Training in open data support

The basics of ethics in research

Research fields concerned*

- Human embryonic stem cells and human embryos
- Humans
- Human cells or tissues
- Personal data
- Animals
- Artificial intelligence

Main ethics issues*

- the respect for persons and for human dignity
- fair distribution of benefits and burden
- the rights and interests of the participants
- participants' free informed consent (with particular attention to vulnerable categories of individuals such as children, patients, discriminated people, minorities, persons unable to give consent, etc.)

How to address the issues

- Participants are volunteers:
 - ethics approvals
 - information sheets and consent forms
- Children:
 - justification for involving them
 - parent consents
- Vulnerable individuals:
 - Ensure that participants are not coerced or induced in any way
- Clinical trials:
 - European and national procedures
- Human cells or tissues:
 - EU regulations and national laws
- Personal data:
 - see the dedicated training
- Animals
 - EU and national animal testing regulations
 - Protected species procedures
- National funders' requirements

*selected examples of the Horizon Europe self-assessment form

Training in open data support

The basics of ethics in research

4

Plan and activities

The ethics committee of the university*

- Role
- Submitting a protocol

The institutional review board of the university*

- Role
- Contact procedure

*if applicable

References

European Commission. How to complete your ethics self-assessment, 2021.
https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/how-to-complete-your-ethics-self-assessment_en.pdf

Task 5.3

University Centres of Support for Open Science

Case 1

**Research Data
Management
and FAIR Data**

Case 2

**Responsible
Publishing**

Case 3

**Citizen
Science**

Case 2: Responsible Publishing

Training in open access publishing

Toolkit 2 – Training in open access publishing – is based on Case #2 – Responsible publishing.

It contains scenarios of two lessons:

- Creating a Diamond (Platinum) Open Access Journal
- Open Access monograph publishing

Training in open access publishing

Lesson plans

Open access should not mean subpar-quality journals or financial strain on authors.

Our Alliance members aim to enhance the diamond open access model, known for sustainability. We want to bring scholarly publishing back to its roots, prioritizing scientists in the process for high standards.

We are dedicated to aiding scientists in starting diamond open access journals and open access monograph projects, offering two lesson plans below.

Lesson 1

Creating a
Diamond
(Platinum) Open
Access Journal:
A guide

Lesson 2

Open Access
monograph
publishing:
A guide

Training in open access publishing

Creating a Diamond (Platinum) Open Access Journal. A guide

Training audience

- Doctoral students
- Researchers
- Staff

Previous knowledge

- Basic knowledge of the journal publishing process (with emphasis on electronic journals), editorial integrity, publishing standard
- Prior review of the 4EU+ webinar material: STRATEGIES FOR PUBLISHING IN OPEN ACCESS JOURNALS | Open for you!
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TIZO1Zq-oMg>

Aims of the training

- Understand the differences among various types of Open Access
- Understand no-fee OA publishing options with emphasis on what is a diamond open journal
- Understand the rights that apply to open access publishing:
 - Copyright transfer agreement
 - Rights retention mechanisms (Plan S, Funder requirements)
 - Self-archiving policies + embargo (repositories)
 - Publication version (VoR, AAM, postprint, preprint)
- Learn what funding models are available for running a diamond open access journal
- Learn to acquire and manage financial resources
- Know indexing databases and directories, such as DOAJ and DOAB
- Know examples of innovative platforms (e.g. ResearchEquals, Octopus)
- Know examples of open peer review practices (e.g. Open Research Europe – F1000Research publishing platform)

Creating a Diamond (Platinum) Open Access Journal. A guide

Plan and activities

Planning a new Diamond Open Access Journal

- Choose the name and define a scope
- Plan the organisational and governance structure
- Form an editorial board
- Decide on the structure, content and layout
- Choose the hosting and data systems
 - Web hosting
 - Domains and Uniform Resource Locator (URL)
 - Backup
 - Archiving
 - Journal management software
- Prepare instructions for authors

Prepare policies state practices, procedures and expectations for authors and readers as recommended by the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE)

- Peer-review policy
- Publication policy / Publisher-Author agreement – authors agree to the publisher licensing the content to appropriate search engines and database providers to ensure maximum exposure of the content to the intended audiences, on the understanding that any income received by the journal is used only to support its development and publication
- Authorship – retain copyright to the material
- Creative Commons licences
- Appropriate review of human subject research policy
- Disclosure of conflicts of interest
- Complaints policy

Examples + Exercise

Creating a Diamond (Platinum) Open Access Journal. A guide

Plan and activities

Prepare policies state practices, procedures and expectations for authors and readers as recommended by the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE)

Examples

- Documentation prepared by other diamond journals searched e.g. at DOAJ
- CC licence types and their meaning
- Platforms with open peer-reviews
- Sample contracts with provisions on rights retention and self-archiving
- Cooperation with libraries:
<https://librarypublishing.org/>

Exercise

- check what submission requirements are in the DOAJ
<https://doaj.org/apply/guide/>
- search available materials on the COPE platform
<https://publicationethics.org/management>
- Find diamond journal initiatives in your country/Europe, e.g. <https://www.diamondopen.com/>

Training in open access publishing

Creating a Diamond (Platinum) Open Access Journal. A guide

Plan and activities

Resource and Financing models

Generating incomes

- Volunteer effort
- Internship
- Personal/Institutional membership fees
- Sponsorship from commercial publishers, information providers and universities/libraries funds
- Donations from readers
- The sale of added-value products (e.g. PDF format, Kindle/epub formats, print on demand paperback)
- Obtaining grants
- Inter-institutional cooperation / Collectively-organised funding (e.g. Open Edition Journals, Diamond Open)
- Shared infrastructure
- Advertisements

Expected costs

- Professional copy-editing
- Translation
- Conversion of articles to XML/XHTML format
- Reference checking
- Indexing and archiving (e.g. LOCKSS system, WebCite consortium – <https://webcitation.org/> which supports permanent archiving of web material cited by authors)
- Web development / OJS PKP development – customised version
- Screening software to check for plagiarism
- Assigning PID to publication like DOI number

Creating a Diamond (Platinum) Open Access Journal. A guide

Plan and activities

Disseminating the Content of the Journal

- ISSN Portal
- CrossRef (DOI)
- Indexes (professional)
- Directories (e.g. DOAJ)
- Content Aggregators (e.g. EBSCOhost)
- Metadata harvesters
- Search engine (e.g. Google, Yahoo!)
- Server log analyzers or services such as Google Analytics

Partnership and utilisation of modern technology

- ResearchEquals
- Octopus
- Open Research Europe

Training in open access publishing

Creating a Diamond (Platinum) Open Access Journal. A guide

Bosman, Jeroen, Frantsvåg, Jan Erik, Kramer, Bianca, Langlais, Pierre-Carl, & Proudman, Vanessa. (2021). OA Diamond Journals Study. Part 1: Findings. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558704>

Becerril, Arianna, Bosman, Jeroen, Bjørnshauge, Lars, Frantsvåg, Jan Erik, Kramer, Bianca, Langlais, Pierre-Carl, Mounier, Pierre, Proudman, Vanessa, Redhead, Claire, & Torny, Didier. (2021). OA Diamond Journals Study. Part 2: Recommendations. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4562790>

Solomon, D. Developing Open Access Journal : A Practical Guide, Chandos Publishing Limited, Oxford, 2008. Version 1.02 2008-06-19:
https://www.uib.no/sites/w3.uib.no/files/attachments/guide_to_developing_oa_journals.pdf

Ševkušić, Milica, Nježić, Irena. Open access publishing: training approaches : The EIFL open science train-the-trainer bootcamp, 2023,
https://europa.eu/youreurope/business/running-business/intellectual-property/rights/index_pl.html

References

Training in open access publishing

Open Access monograph publishing. A guide

Lesson 2

Training audience

- Doctoral students
- Researchers
- Staff

Previous knowledge

- Basic knowledge of the monograph publishing process, editorial integrity, publishing standard, gold and green open access
- Prior review of the 4EU+ webinar material: PUBLICATION STRATEGIES FOR MONOGRAPHS IN HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES | Open for you! https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_5yN5JvTDno

Aims of the training

- Basic barriers blocking open access for monographs
- Benefits of open access monographs publishing
- Publisher selection (specifics of the scientific publishing market)
- Publication costs
- Funding models for open monograph publishing
- Selecting the appropriate Creative Commons licence
- Finding a trustworthy repository and publisher's policy to self-archive
- Available support at 4EU+ universities (OA publication policies of university publishers and available publication platforms)

Training in open access publishing

Open Access monograph publishing. A guide

Plan and activities

Barriers

- Unsustainable business models for small and medium-sized publishers
- Insufficient publication infrastructures
- Harder to maintain the necessary competencies in the rapidly changing publishing landscape
- Print editions of books are continuing importance
- Various forms of books makes it difficult to manage the publishing process
- Submission, peer-review, and editorial processes are less standardised than in the area of journals
- The costs of publishing open access books depend on the volume/type of the document (is much bigger than publishing an article)
- The fear that open access leads to serious shortfalls in the sales of print editions

Benefits

- Visibility (e.g. indexing in DOAB and OAPEN Library)
- Increased reuse
- Readership (diverse audiences)
- Citability (better assessment of the study)
- Authorship acknowledged/control (against plagiarism)
- Wider impact and bigger public engagement
- Complies with the requirements of research funding agencies and the institution's openness policies

Training in open access publishing

Open Access monograph publishing. A guide

Plan and activities

What to look for when selecting a publisher (essentials):

- The OA version of the publication is made visibly accessible on the publisher's website, together with the respective paid versions
- Text and data mining (TDM) are permitted
- OA publications are recorded in corresponding databases such as OAPEN and DOAB
- Authors and editors grant the general public extensive rights of use by granting an Open Access-compliant Creative Commons licence (CC BY or CC BY-SA)
- Rights information is included in text form in the imprint and embedded in the file in a machine-readable form
- A peer review or review process is used for scientific review that meets the usual standards in the field
- There is openness to new, innovative forms of quality assurance, e.g., open peer review
- The publications are published in PDF, XML, HTML formats
- The metadata are as detailed as possible
- Each publication receives a DOI as a persistent identifier. Other possible identifiers are URN and handle, if applicable
- Provide a list of the publication fee if applicable
- The publisher provides information on the added value of an OA publication and advises on legal issues and CC licences
- Usage statistics are presented on the page

Training in open access publishing

Open Access monograph publishing. A guide

Plan and activities

Costs

- Staff costs (Staff time for those working in the following departments: Acquisitions, Manuscript Editorial, Design, and Production)
- Title-specific direct costs (any outsourced work or services directly related to the creation of a monographs)
- Press-level overhead (General and Administrative expenses and Departmental overheads)
- In-kind contributions (these include the many contributions the press may benefit from, but are not paid for, like generating an index)

Examples of the distribution of publication costs →

€1000

Ubiquity

Training in open access publishing

Open Access monograph publishing. A guide

Plan and activities

Examples of the distribution of publication costs

£1000

- Community development
- Submission to prepublication checks
- Peer review management
- Prepublication checks to publication
- Services after publication
- Platform development
- Marketing and business development
- Author and user support

<https://blog.fi000.com/2020/08/19/price-transparency-on-fi000research/>

Training in open access publishing

Open Access monograph publishing.

A guide

Plan and activities

Examples of the distribution of publication costs

Ubiquity

- Full-text peer review
- Providing editorial support (e.g. advice on copyright clearance, ethics matters etc)
- Crossref Similarity Check service
- Cover design
- Metadata, DOI and ISBN registration
- Publication in downloadable PDF, EPUB, MOBI (Kindle) formats as well as in-browser online reading
- Chapter specific landing pages
- Print-on-Demand (POD) service and listing through book retailer websites and distribution lists
- Publication of data, software and media files associated with the book
- Inclusion in search, indexing and aggregation platforms, library catalogues, library suppliers, discovery services, etc.
- Sending print copies of the published book to authors/editors as well as reviewers
- Promotion and marketing
- Full book and chapter specific usage metrics
- Royalty payments to authors/editors from print sales
- Archiving into appropriate repositories, legal deposit and preservation services
- Typesetting and digital file creation
- English language copyediting (CE) will also be added to our services as standard, however, this may be removed to reduce the BPC if the authors are able to provide high quality texts or arrange the copyediting themselves
- Rates at commercial publishers

Examples:

The OpenAPC initiative collects and disseminates datasets on fees paid for open access publishing (also BPC)

<https://openapc.net/>

<https://ubiquity.pub/book-publishing/charges/>

Training in open access publishing

Open Access monograph publishing. A guide

Plan and activities

Publishers of open access books can earn revenue through

- Publication fees (book processing charges, BPCs) and the sale of the print edition (dual publishing), which is often produced using digital print-on-demand technology.
- Other publishers finance the basic costs of their open access segment via crowdfunding (e.g., Knowledge Unlatched, transformative agreements negotiated by consortia) or institutional memberships (e.g., Open Book Publishers [OBP], the Open Library of Humanities [OLH], Language Science Press). Crowdfunding and partnerships:
 - Open Book Publishers
 - Open Humanities Press
 - COPIM (Community-led Open Publication Infrastructure for Monographs)
 - KOALA
 - Knowledge Unlatched (books)
 - SCOAP₃

Creative Commons licence

- CC-BY
- CC-BY-SA
- CC-BY-ND
- CC-BY-NC
- CC-BY-NC-SA
- CC-BY-NC-ND

Trustworthy repository

- Good practice if it is certified and meets the recommendations of the requirements (e.g. CoreTrustSeal)

Training in open access publishing

Open Access monograph publishing. A guide

Lesson 2

Plan and activities

Available publishing support at 4EU+ universities

Examples (gold OA)

- Karolinum Press (CU)
- Tidsskrift.dk (UCPH)
- heiUP (HU)
- heiJOURNALS (HU)
- heiBOOKS (HU)
- UNIMI Journals (UM)
- UNIMI Books (UM)
- IDUB UW BPC fund (UW)

Examples (green OA, institutional repositories)

- Repozitář publikační činnosti UK (CU)
- Sorbonne University HAL repository (SU)
- CURIS (Copenhagen University Research Information System) (UCPH)
- CLARIN-DK-UCPH Repository (UCPH)
- heiDOK – The Heidelberg Document Repository (HU)
- AIR — Institutional Research Repository (UM)
- University of Warsaw Repository, in the process of upgrade (UW)

Training in open access publishing

Open Access monograph publishing. A guide

Arbeitsgemeinschaft Universitätsverlage. (2018). Qualitätsstandards für Open-Access-Monografien und -Sammelbände (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3562239>

CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025 (V01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051012>

Nordhoff, S. (2018). Cookbook for open access books. Language Science Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1286925>

Open Access Books Toolkit (2020, October 29). The OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit. <https://oabooks-toolkit.org/>

Open Access Network. (Last updated: 2022, October 21) Business Models for Books. <https://open-access.network/en/information/financing/business-models-for-books>

Open Access Network. (Last updated: 2023, February 3) Open Access Books. <https://open-access.network/en/information/publishing/open-access-books>

Research Libraries Group & OCLC. (2002). Trusted digital repositories : attributes and responsibilities : an rlg-oclc report. RLG. <https://www.oclc.org/content/dam/research/activities/trustedrep/repositories.pdf>

References

Task 5.3

University Centres of Support for Open Science

**Research Data
Management
and FAIR Data**

**Responsible
Publishing**

**Citizen
Science**

Case 3: Citizen Science

Toolkit 3 – Citizen Science – is based on Case #3 that aimed to explore citizen science (CS) challenges and opportunities within the Train4EU+ Alliance. It investigated CS project best practices and support units, and generated recommendations for enhancing CS projects.

The toolkit contains:

- the descriptions of three citizen science projects from Denmark, France, and the Czech Republic
- the interview guide facilitating collecting data on university support, required competencies, and funding models for CS projects
- citizen science recommendations

Citizen Science Projects

Arter

<https://arter.dk/>

With the help of the website or the app "Arter – reporting" nature enthusiasts can gain knowledge about Denmark's approximately 35.000 species of animals, plants, and fungi.

At the same time, one can create a profile on the website and report occurrences of species. These “finds” are identified and validated by experts and by the community active in the Arter project. Further, the data is freely available for download.

The ambition is to provide a national portal, where all information about Danish biodiversity is collected. At the present time over 50.063.091 findings are registered with over 10.000 unique contributors. The project was launched in May 2021.

Citizen Science Projects

Na suchu

<https://eu-citizen.science/project/361>

This citizen science project started in 2022. It investigates the current state of the agricultural landscape in the Czech Republic. The main goal is to engage farmers, farm landowner or people walking by farmland with taking photos of agricultural areas and uploading the photos on the iNaturalist app.

There are six main subjects of investigation: 1) solitary trees, 2) crops, 3) biobelts and embankments, 4) restoration of dirt roads, 5) pools and areas to retain water, 6) fruit trees in agroforestry fields.

The project addresses changes happening in agricultural landscapes and monitors how these changes affect the landscape. Because the project is for the whole country of the Czech Republic, it is a requirement that a large number of people engage in providing the data.

The aim of Na suchu is to jointly create a database monitoring the impacts of drought in Czech agriculture, to share examples of bad and good practices and thus contribute to a better future in the field of water retention in the landscape, a better yield of fields and more ecological management.

Citizen Science Projects

L'Observatoire
Agricole de la
Biodiversité

<https://www.observatoire-agricole-biodiversite.fr/>

The project is an initiative of the French Ministry of Agriculture and was launched in 2011 to compensate for the lack of surveillance concerning biodiversity. It aims to establish a link between biodiversity research and farmers as well other stakeholders around farming to record relevant biodiversity data.

OAB provides the participants with five different protocols. 1) Solitary bee nestboxes, 2) Butterfly transects, 3) Earthworm plots, 4) terrestrial invertebrate plots 5) bat recordings. The protocols address the broader topics and landscape quality, pollination, soil fertility, pest monitoring, and crop auxiliaries.

Citizen Science Interview Guides

Through a qualitative method of three sequential interviews, we engage in short, focused discussions with minimal time commitment from participants.

This approach allows us to tailor interviews, building on previous discussions and exploring new directions.

We present here interview guides that were used in the three rounds of interviews.

Citizen Science Interview Guide – part 1

About the project

About
the project

- What is the name of the citizen science project?
- Is there a website or source material we can refer to?
- Please collect URL/DOIs (can be filled in before the interview by the expert)
- Who are the citizens in the project, and what data did they need to collect (and how)?
- Did you have support from the university administration – in what form/who?
- Did the library provide support and which form?
- Did you have help from the university IT?
- Did you have help from the university data lab or similar?

Citizen Science Interview Guide – part 2

Experiences running the CS project

Experiences
running
the CS project

- Which citizen science activities were/are in your project?
- Was the project a negative or positive experience?
- What was the greatest success experience you had during the project?
- What was the greatest challenge you faced during the project?
- What could have gone better in your project?

Citizen Science Interview Guide – part 3

Support for Citizen Science (part 1)

Support
for Citizen
Science

- How is citizen science promoted/supported at your university? Who promotes it?
- If none, use the follow-up question:
- How would you like your university to support citizen science?
- Are there policy papers specifically on citizen science at your university?
- A follow-up question, could be to ask if they know of any national citizen science policy.
- Are there citizen science associations, citizen science platforms or other information services on citizen science at your university? If so, please specify them.
- Which support units at the university helped you throughout the project?
- Which technical infrastructure(s) provided support in your project?

Citizen Science Interview Guide – part 3

Support for Citizen Science (part 2)

Support
for Citizen
Science

- Which human infrastructure(s) provided support in your project?
- IF no support, what kind of help would you like to have?
- What requirements or needs exist for handling, cleaning, storing and sharing data in citizen science projects?
- Which aspects of support are citizen science specific and which are support “agnostic” support?
- Where and when in the process around a citizen science project is the support most needed?
- What support did/will you on reflection need?
- Which gaps in support do you see?
- How are the researchers best supported in connection with citizen science projects at the moment and how could this be optimized?

Citizen Science Interview Guide – part 4

About skills and training

About skills
and training

- Which skills do each stakeholder group need (including yourself in running and administering the project)?
- Does your university run citizen science courses or training programs (on which level)?
- Did the [stakeholder group] receive training to take part in your project?
- Do you plan for stakeholder training?
- Which gaps in skills development do you see?

Citizen Science Interview Guide – part 5

Funding (part 1)

Funding

- How was the project funded?
- What is the name of the funder(s) and are there are requirements that the project has to fulfill according to the funder (compliance)?
- Tell me more about your funder(s), are they national, international, institutional or a mix?
- What are the requirements from your funder(s)?
- What does the funding cover/not cover (budget costs)?
- What does the funding cover or not cover compared to the budget costs that you have?
- What are your experiences regarding getting EU funding?

Citizen Science Interview Guide – part 5

Funding (part 2)

Funding

- Any particular difficulties or opportunities in getting citizen science projects funded?
- Have you tried to crowdfund your projects? Third party funding?
- Do you know of any other funding possibilities for citizen science projects? If yes, who funds citizen science projects in which area?
- Which model of investment would you like to see?
- Speculative question: What would be your preferable, optimal model of support for your project?

Citizen Science Recommendations

These recommendations may contribute to developing a strategy towards infrastructures and support models for citizen science.

Each recommendation has the potential to enhance the value of citizen science research at the individual university and through collaboration inside, across and outside the universities of the 4EU+ Alliance.

Recommended support

1

University libraries, university IT support and data stewards need to collaborate to provide technical support in concretely developing and setting up suitable platforms/databases/infrastructures for CS projects. Further, they need to facilitate user-experience tests in platform development in CS projects. Such platforms have the responsibility to balance the data collection process, depth of data and technical platform to the needs of researchers, scientific integrity and amateur contributors.

2

Provide training in communication strategies and how to conduct stakeholder analyses or budget for a communication officer in the CS project application.

3

Take advantage of the opportunities to use university libraries and public libraries as relevant platforms to reach new target groups who can be involved in CS projects for the benefit of democratisation of knowledge, research and the population's interest in science.

4

Based on the fact that in one of the investigated CS projects no support was provided from the university's IT department or the university as such it is considered to be beneficial to create a place where resources related to CS are gathered. This might also strengthen the progress and synergy in relation to other CS projects within the university.

5

For the countries without a tradition of and experience with CS consider to support top-down initiatives such as nationwide CS projects.

Recommended infrastructure – part 1

1

Recognise that CS projects are different from other research projects and hence require other forms of support. University policy papers need to clarify how the university will benefit from CS projects to be able to advocate for investment in resources for citizen science projects.

2

Support for CS projects could include a single point of contact for CS (SPOC) at the university or national competence center. Support at the SPOC could be provided in two streams, human infrastructure and technical infrastructure.

- **Human infrastructure:** a “hub” (lab or office) that offers advice in how to design a CS project, where to find funding, recruitment and retainment of citizens, communication and promotion strategies and how citizens and other stakeholders feel validated in their contribution to the project. Further the hub could provide knowledge of applications and technical solutions for data collection and handling, including expertise in ethical and legal considerations regarding data collected by citizens.
- **Technical infrastructure:** provide safe storage for data, and data collection devices for researchers to use in training and promotion of projects. In particular, guidance in how to build an easy-to-use-platform that citizens can use to deliver relevant, quality data and researchers can use to process the data and provide sustainable outcomes.

Recommended infrastructure – part 2

3

It is a core responsibility of the university to promote research. A communication channel should be provided by the university or between universities where researchers and citizens are able to exchange knowledge, interests, projects and recruitment. This could be the face of the university in society and contribute to reducing the distance between research institutions and citizens, increasing trust in science and in the application of results.

4

Invest in the education or up-skilling of communication experts. Continued communication is essential throughout a CS project and requires skills in science communication across diverse groups of stakeholders. The following profiles are identified as key performers in CS projects which require professionalization and identification of a minimum viable skill set:

- A CS Steward: the CS steward has an advisory role and provides guidance on how to run the CS project and identify target groups in the community and design the CS project to fit them. The steward would have knowledge about user-experience and design of data collection and delivery tools, and act as a facilitator who could create connections between persons who want to contribute to CS projects and researchers who have a CS project that needs volunteers.
- CS “champions”. Students or members of the community (citizens) who help with the face-to-face promotion of the project. The champion goes from library to library, from museum to museum, and talks about the CS project with the public.
- A “Community manager” (facilitator). A project member (researcher or administrator) with the responsibility and people skills to continuously work with the community and navigate between stakeholders across the project. They would ensure communication with the community, nurture relationships with stakeholders, gather up and solve issues, collect results and make sure the community is heard and valued in the project.

Recommended funding models

1

Develop standardized and transparent quality criteria for CS projects to grade CS projects in funding rounds

2

Develop templates in EU funders' grant applications, such as Horizon Europe, that fit the description of and elements in a CS project.

3

Pool positions of project "facilitators" from several projects in order to then compile a full position CS community manager who could oversee the communication of multiple CS projects. Community management could also be in cooperation with interested partner organizations or NGO's.

4

Funding opportunities that support conditional financing of long-term projects. Conditional financing, that is the project continues to reach goals and have momentum, would secure funding and safeguard not only the maintenance but also the evolution of the project.

5

Develop funding models that are specifically designed to support CS projects, that is the research, the citizens and the technical and human infrastructures that are unique to CS projects. However, CS funding should not be limited exclusively to specific funding schemes. Rather, it must also be possible to apply for CS projects in the regular funding programs of third-party funders.